

SIGNIFICANCE OF KARAKALPAK FOLK SONGS

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Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda tereń mazmunlılıǵı hám tematikalıq kóptúrliligi menen xalqımızdıń ruwxıy miyraslarınıń dúrdanaları sıpatında insanlardıń kewlinen orın alǵan, búgingi kúnge shekem mángi saqlanıp qalǵan qaraqalpaq xalıq qosıqlarınıń janrlıq áhmiyeti hám ózgeshelikleri haqqında sóz etemiz.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы поговорим о жанровом значении и особенностях каракалпакских народных песен, сохранившихся в сердцах людей как шедевры духовного наследия нашего народа с их глубоким смыслом и тематическим разнообразием.

Annotation: In this article, we will talk about the genre significance and features of the Karakalpak folk songs, which have been preserved in the hearts of people as masterpieces of the spiritual heritage of our people with their deep meaning and thematic diversity.

Gilt sózler: *mádeniyat, kórkem óner, xalıq awızeki dóretpeleri, xalıq qosıqları, milliy namalar.*

Ключевые слова: *культура, искусство, фольклор, народные песни, народные песни.*

Keywords: *culture, art, folklore, folk songs, national songs.*

Cultural heritage is always considered a great weapon of the nation, it helps to forget the difficult times of our ancestors in the past, takes spiritual nourishment from them, and strengthens their confidence in a prosperous life in the future.

The most important of them are folk songs, most of which were performed by our jiraws. It has been preserved for centuries in wonderful epics such as "Alpamis", "Máspatsha", "Sháryar", "Goruglı", "Edige", "Qirq qiz", "Qoblan" and other oral works of the people, and they have passed through the path of teaching from father to son, from teacher to student, and have reached the present day.²⁵

²⁵ Адамбаева Т., Жиемуратов М. Жыраў намалары. Нөкис: Қарақалпақстан, 1991. Б-5.

The main content of the heroic epics of Karakalpak also made the people strive for this goal. In the positive images of the heroes in these works, the strong national feelings of young people, which have a strong educational value in protecting their people, are embodied.

Researchers Q. Ayımbetov, Q. Maqsetov, K. Mámbetov, S. Bakhadirova, A. Allamuratov, T. Adambaeva and several other scientists have provided information about the history of literature, the craft of epic writing, and folk oral creativity. It is reported that they date back to the time of Soppasli Sipira Jiraw, Qorqit ata (XIV century), who are considered to be the deep roots of the singing art of our people.

However, no one can deny the fact that singing, music, and dance entertainment are an integral part of people's daily life and are invaluable spiritual food, and they have been living at all stages of human society.

«... Saz benen sáwbetti yalǵan demeńler,

Adam ata binyad bolǵanda bardı»

these lines of the song clearly confirm the above opinion.

Regardless of the time, the people are close to them, they did not let their favorite songs out of their mouths, good songs were the tireless wings of people, they listened and sang when they were tired and depressed, inspired them and turned their dream into his spiritual heritage, leaving it to the next generation. Once upon a time, the sound of bakshi-jirov, the music of musicians singing at weddings, spread far and wide, and the villagers sat and listened to them tirelessly until dawn.

In the years of independence, international musical relations have been developing along the path of non-political, rather free relations. "After our country gained independence, the people's hearts were filled with songs involuntarily. I am not a singer or a poet. If Allah had given me such a profession, I would have given songs with good words to all of you, to my country." - said our president I. A. Karimov.²⁶

²⁶ Каримов И.А. Янги Ўзбекистоннинг 7-зафари йили. Шарқ нашриёти матбаа концертини бош тахририяти. - Тошкент, 1999.- 5 б.

People's songs, with their deep meaning, thematic diversity, and various colors, have been memorized and preserved in the hearts of people as masterpieces of the spiritual heritage of our people. Their educational importance is also very great. Mother Song, all songs from lullabies to our youth and adults sing, exhort our children to acquire high humanitarian virtues in the future, every citizen should be self-confessed, single-minded, and earthy-hearted, to love his motherland, to protect the country from the enemy, appreciate true friendship, maintaining morality, not to be conceited, the most original qualities, such as generosity.

Karakalpak folk songs are different from the songs of other peoples, and another aspect is that in each song, the life path of our people, the way of making a diary is clearly visible. Therefore, the songs that reflected the truth of history were carefully kept by people as the property of the people, an inexhaustible gold-treasure.

Each song has its own era and history. No matter which one we choose, the sound of its time is heard there, sometimes it stirs deep thoughts, it gives joy to a person in difficult and difficult times, sometimes it looks like a flag, it raises the spirit of people and starts them to courage. It is clear that the words of songs in any epic that are widespread among the people, and the words that are performed by dutor, kobiz, gijjak and other instruments in their songs, were created by well-known people. However, with the passage of time, the names of the first people who created them were forgotten or not mentioned, and they came to the next generation with the terms "xaliq dastani", "xaliq qosigi" or "xaliq namasi".²⁷

In these songs, the positive images of the heroes embody the greatness of the youth and the national sentiments that have a strong educational value in protecting their country. Thus, music conveys reality, artistic images to human consciousness through artistic sounds. When we play a well-known piece of music, we imagine events that have happened or are happening in a person's life. It shows that music has some kind of power.

Karakalpak national music art developed over centuries has its own deep and life-sustaining veins. The main task of today's art lovers and scientists is to study this national cultural heritage from the scientific side, to spread it widely among the people, to preserve

²⁷ Аманиязов Ф. Тарийҳқа айланған қосықлар //Жипек жолы. -Нөкис, 2007. - №25.

national folk songs and pass them on to future generations by enriching them with the achievements of world music art.

REFERENCES

1. Адамбаева Т., Жиёмуратов М. Жыраў намалары. Нөкис: Қарақалпақстан, 1991.
2. Каримов И.А. Янги Узбекистоннинг 7-зафари йили. Шарқ нашриёти матбаа концертини бош тахририяти. - Тошкент, 1999.
3. Аманиязов Ғ. Тарийхқа айланған қосықлар //Жипек жолы. -Нөкис, 2007. - №25.